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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 7.3 – DESIGN GUIDELINES AND VALIDATION REPORTS FOR PRIVACY [FIRST VERSION]

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Executive summary

The document outlines the first outcomes from Task T7.4: "Definition of Privacy Guidelines," "Design guidelines and validation reports for privacy (first version)". This task builds on the work presented in D2.3, which focused on identifying privacy requirements related to the project. The guidelines were developed based on the identified requirements, an extensive analysis of relevant literature on the principles of designing for accountable and ethical Extended Reality (XR), additional steps taken to validate the developed technologies against current industrial benchmarks for ethical work, transparency, and privacy, and paradigms and findings from co-design sessions with end-users and stakeholders, which relate to the development of privacy and ethics control mechanisms (described in details in D2.3 and D3.3). We designed these guidelines to be applicable in the context of designing XR solutions for industrial work, primarily involving off-highway machinery. The results of this deliverable will prompt further privacy-related considerations in the project, informing the assessment criteria in D6.7. "Privacy assessment results". It will also be updated based on ongoing work with project stakeholders and summarized in the report of D7.6 "Design guidelines and validation reports for privacy (final version)", which will include the validation reports for privacy and ethics with internal project stakeholders and external auditory (via receiving feedback from the broader industry of Off-Highway Machinery). The document comprises the following sections: a) an overview of current approaches to ethical and security guidelines in XR b) an outline of the challenges in developing of XR solutions for off-highway machinery; c) a set of guidelines focused on privacy and ethical considerations in XR projects, derived from elicited privacy requirements and values considerations and developed in collaboration with stakeholders. The validation procedures and validation report will be presented in the D7.6 "Design guidelines and validation reports for privacy (final version).

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1 Introduction

The integration of XR elements into working contexts is becoming one of the core components of the ongoing new industrial revolution. While most attention is currently focused on potential applications in gaming and social interaction, XR is also being increasingly implemented in various job processes, such as in medical and industrial settings. When discussed within the broader framework of XR, practitioners and scholars typically associate several groups of potential effects of XR implementations with privacy and work ethics considerations. First, while operating, XR technologies are capable of collecting a diverse range of data. This data can include operational parameters, environmental conditions, and even operator physiological data, such as gaze direction or physical force applied to a haptic device. It can also provide data that creates a comprehensive view of the operator's psychological state (e.g., pupil dilation and the tempo of object movements can be combined to suggest that the operator feels extremely nervous). Another issue widely discussed in the XR community is the problem of users' interactions with the output of XR technologies. For example, people may start unintentionally mixing real and virtual objects and disproportionately rely on these "extended" parts of reality to perform their tasks. Finally, many XR-related applications heavily rely on AI-powered algorithms that use sensitive user data to enhance their features. Consequently, the development of XR solutions also raises issues concerning the transparency and fairness of these algorithms, as well as the ability to retrieve data from them. In addition to the specific challenges associated with different XR technology applications, implementing XR in the workplace (especially in the context of industrial machinery) introduces additional difficulties for developers. First, newly developed XR solutions often aim to be integrated into existing organizational or technological workflows. This requires a thorough analysis of the existing organizational and technological processes to ensure that new technologies can be seamlessly incorporated without disrupting current operations. As XR technologies are still relatively new in industrial applications compared to other sectors, such as entertainment, stakeholders are typically sceptical, especially in industries with previously low levels of digitalization, such as in certain off-highway machinery sectors. The low to moderate digitalization levels also imply that introducing XR technologies, such as 'always-on' sensors or cameras, could significantly increase the collection of personal data from workers and bystanders, a practice that could not previously be governed by workplace privacy regulation. Moreover, since the collected data become intertwined with work processes and can be potentially used to assess employee performance, the extensive data collection enabled by XR poses serious ethical questions about the balance between operational efficiency (business interests) and employees' rights for privacy and other human rights on the working place. In environments where XR technologies are utilized, every action, decision, and even minor lapses can potentially be recorded and analysed. This level of monitoring could create a culture of constant surveillance, leading to a stressful and potentially intrusive work environment. The ethical challenge here concerns the degree to which the use of XR technologies can improve (or at least keep in with the industry's standards) an employee's right to privacy and autonomy.

The mentioned challenges require actionable and practical-oriented guidelines that can govern the development and implementation of XR technologies in the workplace context of off-highway machinery. These guidelines must ensure that XR technologies enhance workplace functionality without posing new challenges to employee privacy or autonomy. Furthermore, the guidelines should be designed to foster a transparent environment where the use of XR technologies is clearly communicated to all stakeholders, ensuring that they understand the scope and purpose of data collection and monitoring. While several research groups and organizations have started to propose and promote guidelines for the development

of XR applications, only a few have extensively focused on the ethical values and principles that should be integrated into XR-powered solutions [20, 26]. To the best of our knowledge, there are no existing guidelines aimed at outlining how to incorporate principles of ethical work and privacy considerations into the development of industrial XR, specifically in off-highway machinery context. Building on our extensive work on Privacy Requirements for THEIA^{XR} project, we have expanded the formulated requirements and provided verified guidelines for applying these (and similar) requirements to the process of developing XR-related workplace enhancements.

2 Privacy and ethics questions in Extended Reality

The current research in XR recognizes that developing solutions in augmented, mixed, and virtual reality can pose significant risks to ethics and privacy [3, 13, 16, 22, 33]. The main issue mentioned in this context is that user behaviour data generated by AR could be exploited without users' consent, leading to user identification [12, 19]. This risk is heightened when linked with other existing databases, such as Facebook [26]. Huang et al. discuss a similar problem in the context of the virtual reality space (Metaverse), pointing out the potential privacy leakage of biometric information, which can be easily de-anonymized via Facebook users' profiles [19]. Giarretta also pointed to the fact that integration of Virtual Reality in the social networking domain can also push users to disclose more personal private data than in just general VR settings [16]. Khamis and Alt highlight AR's privacy and security issues, including the unintentional disclosure of confidential data, the complexity of obtaining informed consent, and emerging vulnerabilities for attacks [22]. The global ethical problem related to this group of privacy concerns is associated with the possibility of mass surveillance of users from the company's side. Furthermore, the technologies can collect data that may disclose information about the user, of which even they are not aware (e.g., micromovements can be analyzed from a health perspective), potentially leading to discriminatory actions toward the person [30]. Another issue arises from the fact that companies often fail to provide users with comprehensive information about the data collected and its potential uses. Even when efforts are made to inform users, research from other domains indicates that many users choose not to read privacy notices due to their lengthy and legalistic language. This problem is exacerbated in the context of XR systems, where the sensitivity of the potentially collected data heightens the concerns. Ethical and security concerns arise from the spatial constraints in virtual environments, potentially manipulating user choices and revealing frequented locations [6, 16]. At the level of specific technologies, research efforts have primarily focused on eye-tracking technology (e.g., [9, 32]); however, several studies are dedicated to the problem of privacy in wearable sensors [33]. The issue identified in this domain is that technologies like eye-tracking in mixed reality, while enhancing virtual object placement, risk exposing sensitive user information, such as preferences and mental load, often without explicit consent [32]. Several studies emphasized experts' and users' concerns in XR about the lack of user awareness regarding data collection, opaque practices by XR developers, and potential manipulative tactics by malicious agents, exploiting these issues and XR's unique characteristics [2, 4, 17, 18]. Despite some studies suggesting limited user concerns over data privacy in XR, a persistent apprehension about privacy in augmented environments remains [4]. In the study by Hadan et al., the authors identified factors that influenced users' concerns about data privacy in XR, describing systems that collect cognitive, emotional, and personality data as "too intrusive." The study also indicated an increase in users' discomfort if the XR device operated "in the background." Additionally, the perception of algorithmic unfairness in data collection contributed to the level of users' discomfort [17]. At the same time, the study of O'Hagan et al. showed users low awareness but high concern about AR headset activities, particularly those related to bystanders' data [29].

2.1 Frameworks and guidelines in privacy and ethics of work in XR

Legal scholars have highlighted the importance of regulatory measures to protect users in Extended Reality (XR) environments [37]. Despite this, there are limited frameworks available for evaluating potential risks. Reilly et al. proposed a framework and software implementation for prototyping and developing usable security solutions for Mixed Reality in one of the first works in the domain. The framework aimed to synchronize privacy-related actions across both physical and virtual spaces. The key features of the tool include a shared ontology for physical-virtual interaction, a flexible communication model, and interface mechanisms that support a seamless user experience across realities [34]. De Guzman et al. [10], based on extensive analysis of the literature, summarised a list of security and privacy concerns that arise in Mixed Reality. This list included various privacy model attributes, such as integrity, non-repudiation, availability, authorization, and authentication. Additionally, it covers aspects like identification, confidentiality, anonymity, pseudonymity, unlinkability, unobservability, undetectability, plausible deniability, content

awareness, and compliance with policies and consent. The authors suggests safeguarding five key areas: data input, data itself, data output, user interaction, and device protection. Another noteworthy approach is the XRSI Privacy Framework by the XR Safety Initiative [20]. This framework focuses on assessing privacy risks, informing users about these risks, managing privacy, and preventing privacy-related incidents in XR settings. It also integrates these concerns within the broader context of Human-Centric Privacy by Design. Moreover, the XRSI framework aligns its measures with major legal privacy and compliance standards like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA). The report from the IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality aimed to identify key privacy challenges produced by Extended Reality and suggested a list of recommendations for developers on how to address these issues. The main challenges identified by the framework were related to extensive sensory and behavioural data collection, which can be processed to infer personal details beyond the user’s intention. This includes the ability to de-anonymize users, as the precision of data captured by XR devices can uniquely identify individuals based on their physical or behavioural traits. Additionally, there is the potential to access and analyse profound cognitive and mental data, problems with the unintentional collection of bystanders’ data, and issues related to mass surveillance [26]. The 15 recommendations presented in the form of suggestions from design and legislation highlighted the preferable ways and best practices to address the challenges [26]. Norval et al. assert that Extended Reality (XR) systems are intrinsically linked to their environment and user actions. This inherent contextuality presents significant challenges in maintaining transparency and accountability, as it’s difficult to foresee and address potential issues. The physical nature of XR means that problems can lead to immediate and serious consequences, such as injury, property damage, or even more severe outcomes, which go beyond the usual data-related issues. As a result, it’s crucial to focus on how XR systems can be audited. This involves being able to reconstruct or comprehend the system’s behaviour and its context during operation. The authors developed and tested a framework with experts to assist XR system developers. This framework aims to facilitate the capture and management of data necessary for conducting audits and ensuring. While not proposing the exact framework, Abraham et al. explored the concept of fine-granular permission control for applications in XR. They found that this approach helps users better understand the balance between system performance and data collection, allowing them to make more informed decisions about their privacy [1]. The E3XR framework, developed by Lee and Hu-Au [24], evaluates XR technologies across three dimensions: ethics, educational efficacy, and eudaimonia (human flourishing). Ethics is defined in terms of user privacy, autonomy, and avoiding harm. Education is viewed as immersive interactive experiences that enhance learning. Eudaimonia assesses XR’s capacity to promote personal growth and social good, advocating for inclusivity and empowerment. This framework aims to ensure that XR technologies are socially responsible, ethical, and educational integral. The brief overview of the discussed frameworks is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the existing XR frameworks for privacy and ethical development.

Framework title	Description	High-level categories of the framework	Provided suggestions (brief, non-exhaustive summary)
E3XR: An Analytical Framework for Ethical, Educational, and Eudaimonic XR Design [24].	The framework evaluates XR technologies across three dimensions: ethics, educational efficacy, and eudaimonia. It intended to guide the	Ethics, Educational Efficacy, and Eudaimonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage diverse user groups in the design and testing. Incorporate ethical considerations (user autonomy, privacy, and avoiding harm) explicitly in the design process. Ensure that design practices promote transparency, and that user consent is obtained for data collection and usage. Develop and use tools to assess the ethical, educational, and eudaimonic impacts of XR applications.

	design of XR technologies, focusing on maximizing ethical integrity, learning outcomes, and human well-being		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design XR applications that support personal growth and contribute positively to the user's well-being. • Avoid creating applications that simplify complex social issues or reinforce stereotypes. • Design applications that encourage prosocial behaviour. • Prioritize user safety.
Framework for Developing Transparent and Auditable XR [28].	The framework supports developers in making Extended Reality (XR) systems auditable. It focuses on transparency and accountability by enabling the capture and management of audit data during system operation.	<p>General Considerations: considerations about intent, stakeholders, risks, and resources;</p> <p>Capture Considerations: input, output, and operation.</p> <p>Record Considerations : how captured data is recorded, managed, processed, and protected.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the primary aims and functionalities of the XR system, and anticipate potential risks. • Identify all relevant stakeholders ensuring their needs and concerns are considered in the audit process. • Analyse and prepare for risks associated with the technology • Determine the technical, financial, and human resources necessary for implementing and maintaining auditability • Focus on specific system components (e.g., sensors, user interface) for data extraction and determine the most relevant data points. • Identify all potential sources of data input and output within the system (e.g. sensors information, users interaction etc) • Recognize and manage the privacy implications of data capture, complying with legal standards. • Decide on secure and compliant data storage methods. • Define policies for the lifespan of recorded data, including retention periods and conditions for data deletion. • Develop mechanisms for creating comprehensive and tamper-evident audit • Set up protocols for reporting audit findings to stakeholders, enabling them to review and act on the information effectively.
IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Extended Reality (XR) [26].	The framework addresses the ethical considerations and challenges associated with Extended Reality technologies,	Concepts of XR sensing and imputed data, identity and anonymity of self, augmented intelligence and mental privacy, identity and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • XR stakeholders should develop and support efforts to standardize privacy protocols like differential privacy. • XR applications should ensure that the mental privacy and cognitive liberties of users are not violated. • XR applications should clearly disclose what personal data is being captured, how it is being

	<p>focusing on problems of anonymity and privacy. It aims to establish standards that enhance privacy and ethical practices in XR applications</p>	<p>privacy of bystanders, world scraping and distributed surveillance, augmented perception</p>	<p>processed, to what ends, and the duration for which it is retained.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users should have the agency over their data and should be provided with clear information. • When bystander data is legally permissible to capture and process, bystanders should be made aware that this capture is occurring. • There should be regulations to protect real-time surveillance of public and private spaces. • Industry, legislators, and researchers need to define an Extended Reality Privacy Rights Framework to inform future legislation. • XR platforms should control what sensor APIs applications can utilize, and protect data from unintended processing.
<p>Structured list of privacy concerns and solutions from the paper "Security and Privacy Approaches in Mixed Reality: A Literature Survey" [10]</p>	<p>The review summarise the security and privacy problems in mixed reality, providing a possible solutions to mitigate the problems.</p>	<p>Categories of discussion: input protection, data protection, output protection, interaction protection, device protection</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement user-defined policies to control the detail level of sensitive data exposed to applications. • Use environmental policies or systems that automatically detect and sanitize sensitive data captured by MR devices. • Employ systems like Prepose, which allows gesture recognition while ensuring that raw gesture data is not exposed to applications. Implement privacy-preserving data aggregation techniques. • Utilize encryption • Employ techniques that allow data to be processed by multiple parties without any one party having access to all the data. • Implement frameworks that manage how outputs from different applications are rendered, implement systems that ensure data about the environment or other sensitive outputs are not unnecessarily exposed to applications or other users. • Use systems that manage how data is shared among users in a collaborative MR environment, ensuring that all participants have appropriate levels of access and that sensitive information is protected. • Implement mechanisms that control the flow of information across the boundaries of different users' environments. • Ensure that MR devices authenticate users and control access based on user identity, preventing unauthorized use and protecting user data. • Use techniques to physically secure MR devices, preventing tampering and ensuring that the data contained within is secure.

<p>XRSI Privacy Framework [20].</p>	<p>The guidelines curated by the XR Safety Initiative provides a structured approach with focus areas, functions, and controls to help organizations match their strategies with privacy protection in line with international data protection initiatives (GDPR, CCPA)</p>	<p>The framework discuss four basic categories: ASSESS (AS): Privacy Risk Assessment, INFORM (IN): Informing Users about Privacy Risks, MANAGE (MN): Privacy Risk Management, PREVENT (PR): Prevent Privacy Incidents; it also outlines three levels of privacy expectations: Minimum, which is driven by legal mandates and lack of options; desired, which is based on users' emotional investment; and ideal, which represents the optimal privacy state users aim for.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess (AS) – Privacy Risk Assessment: organisation should identify what data is collected, how it is used, and the legal basis for its collection; organizations should evaluate privacy risks associated with the data they handle. • Inform (IN) – Informing Users about Privacy Risks • Organizations must provide clear and comprehensive privacy policies that inform users about data collection, usage, sharing, and protection practices, and assure the consent is clearly given • Manage (MN) – Privacy Risk Management: work-based education of employees, constant monitoring of the policies; handling the privacy incidents; additional protective measures for sensitive data • Prevent (PR) – Prevent Privacy Incidents: clear distribution in roles of data protection, organisation of leveled access to the data, implementation of encryption, content moderation policies
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3 XR applications in industry and in the domain of off-highway machinery:

To date, there has been a limited number of studies and case discussions dedicated to the use of Extended Reality (XR) in the off-highway machinery domain. Even in the existing research, the focus on XR applications has been mostly limited to specific uses. For instance, a systematic literature review by Zoleykani et al. found that most studies on XR in construction primarily discuss its application in design aspects of construction projects, with operational aspects being less frequently addressed [38]. The authors noted that while there is potential to apply XR in end-user applications such as operator safety training, this application is largely seen as a subject for future research. Similarly, in discussing XR applications in the agricultural domain—

which overlaps with off-highway machinery—Fountas et al. mentioned benefits like the teleoperation of agricultural tractors[15]. However, they also noted that this has not yet been implemented in actual agricultural processes. In the broader setting of creating XR solutions in manufacturing, studies showed the applicability of certain MR and VR approaches in different stages of manufacturing; for example, VR can be mostly used in the designing phase, while MR technologies can be already applicable in the whole industrial cycle [14]. In the literature review dedicated to the aspects of AR implementations in industry, the majority of AR applications in industrial environments focus on providing work instructions for manual assembly processes, maintenance, and training. Additionally, AR is used for improving safety in human-robot operations (e.g., by showing the robot’s movement trajectory to the human) and in the broader context of on-site analysis, evaluation, and decision-making [11]. Similarly, based on the systematic literature review provided by Vasarainen et al., there is a growing discussion on using XR to improve existing working practices, especially in stressful and dangerous situations. However, certain existing limitations, such as the level of precision and seamlessness of interaction, make the use of XR problematic in some professional fields. Additionally, the relative novelty of the technology can cause operators to focus more on the virtual aspect of the interaction, potentially neglecting the real-world situation [36]. Summarizing the discussed findings, we can conclude that while both industry and scholars agree on the importance of XR technologies for the further development of industrial processes, including those related to off-highway machinery, the area is still underdeveloped and requires both further technological improvements and extensive user studies to understand the conditions of XR technology acceptance in the industrial context.

4 Development of guidelines for privacy and ethical work for XR enhancements for off-highway machinery:

4.1 Methodology

Developing the Guidelines for Privacy and Ethical Work for XR Enhancements for Off-Highway Machinery, we applied the following procedure:

- First, we conducted a series of interviews with end-users to determine their perceived needs for privacy and control over their data (described in detail in D2.3).
- Second, we organized a series of workshops with other stakeholders and developers to identify relevant privacy challenges in the development of XR solutions for off-highway machinery, incorporating insights received from the users. We also categorized the challenges into those applicable to our research project and those that may pose further risks in future exploration or different development setups for off-highway machinery. The structure of the workshops and the main findings are presented in D2.3 and D3.3
- Third, we conducted three additional in-depth interviews with industry experts in each of our use case domains to better understand the state-of-the-art privacy and ethics in the industries and align future technological visions with the need to preserve privacy and ethics. The interview guide is added to the Appendix; we also conducted a series of workshops with end users to understand their ethical concerns about technology. More details about the motivation behind the interview questions and workshop guides can be found in deliverable D3.3.

- Fourth, we triangulated the results of the expert interviews, stakeholders' privacy discussions, and an extensive analysis of privacy-related frameworks in mixed reality. We also examined guidelines developed in the privacy domain for different types of technologies, such as mobile applications. Since we are working within the framework of European Union standards, we specifically oriented our approach to the structure applied by the European Commission for their standards of privacy for different technologies.

As General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) standards are ultimately applicable to all EU-developed technologies [31], our guidelines did not focus much on the legal data protection aspect of XR-implementation's development. Instead, we oriented towards practical user-centred design measures aimed at providing high-level design frameworks and offering food for thought for future specific implementations. Following the approach to guidelines for designing for privacy discussed by Lederer et al.[23], we need to stress that adhering to the provided principles does not necessarily guarantee privacy-compliant and ethical XR-enhancement implementations. However, not following them probably creates a channel for privacy and ethics breaches. The proposed guidelines are compatible with more general XR privacy frameworks like XRSI and can be used as a complementary procedure for applying XRSI to the off-highway machinery domain. We believe that this first edition of the Guidelines will help spark discussions among different stakeholders across the off-highway machinery domain, guiding us to refine future versions of the guidelines.

4.2 Relevant privacy and ethics challenges of XR development in the off-highway machinery context

4.2.1 Presence of bystanders at the operation sites

As mentioned in [26, 30], protecting the privacy and identity of individuals in locations where XR tracking is operational is crucial. Although the captured data may not inherently violate privacy, the authors demonstrated that when combined with existing extensive databases (such as social media platforms), this data poses significant privacy risks. In the case of off-highway machinery, the risk of collecting bystanders' data is high, as XR-powered machines are planned to operate in semi-enclosed areas of everyday city landscapes (such as during construction), resorts (like snow grooming operations) or in the restricted (by available for other workers and technical specialists) territory of a loading terminal. These environments, however, can also include situations where other workers or the general public may be present and captured by XR solutions without their explicit consent. It is also important to mention that in these cases, bystanders are probably not aware of the presence of capturing technologies, as they have just started to be introduced in industrial settings, so their understanding of privacy risks is expected to be extremely limited.

4.2.2 State of the art for digitalization in the industry and existing business processes

The interviews with experts showed that the level of digitalization in different areas of off-highway machinery is still not high and may distinctly vary from one service provider to another. While in all three discussed cases, the experts acknowledged the ongoing discussion about common data-sharing protocols and a standardized approach to developing technologies, it is still an not fully finished process. Moreover, despite the interest, there are no existing and widely shared XR implementations in the industry. This means that, during the transition to a more digitalized version of processes, including XR enhancements, it is important

to ensure the continuity and operability of businesses without creating dramatic and disruptive changes. This poses the question of how to seamlessly integrate XR processes into existing business processes within an organization. From the point of view of privacy and ethics, it can be formulated as follows: a) how can we ensure that added XR practices do not create additional privacy risks compared to the existing baseline of the working process (which, at this point, mostly does not collect any personal data due to the low digitalization of vehicles), and b) how can we be sure that XR implementation will not create risks of unethical data use (e.g., performance evaluation without the worker's knowledge and consent) or unethical workflow (e.g., over-guidance or provocation of overreliance, as pointed out by the experts in the study by Ursin et al. [35] in the context of a medical setting, which requires similar levels of concern).

4.2.3 24-Hours a day data collection

As was pointed out in the previous works, the multiple sensors and cameras in XR setups can produce increased risks for privacy [26]; this becomes especially relevant in the case of off-highway machinery sensors, which are usually running during full operation; additionally, the areas like container terminal or construction site usually monitored 24 hours a day to assure security of the space. However, it creates a possibility of creating mass surveillance, which in the augmented reality case raises problems with capturing private data from different actors.

4.2.4 High cost of overreliance and other types of cognitive mistakes while operating the vehicle

While we briefly discussed the problem in the section dedicated to the Digitalisation State-of-the-Art in the industry, we believe it requires additional discussion. When improperly operated, most off-highway machinery can pose serious risks to the general safety of drivers and bystanders. The issue of misinterpretation of XR information in this setting becomes even more problematic compared to gaming or other personal use applications. For example, previous studies have shown the possibilities of cybersecurity attacks, which can trigger user mistakes and lead to potential physical harm [7]. However, misguidance is also possible in the case of system errors, even without a malicious agent behind it. During discussions with end-users about possible implementations, experienced operators expressed their high-level concerns about situations where students might use the features of XR systems extensively without considering other parameters (e.g., machine indicators and weather conditions). Consequently, they might not be able to identify situations where systems misbehave or provide false information. This could lead operators into potentially dangerous situations as they might over-rely on the XR system's outputs without critically assessing the accuracy or relevance of the information. In such scenarios, the lack of cross-referencing with real-world indicators could result in hazardous decision-making, which can lead to harming the operator and damaging the vehicle.

4.2.5 Use of AI models to improve the algorithms of XR solutions operation

The integrated XR technologies, like obstacle detection, require advanced machine learning algorithms [5] and large datasets to improve their abilities. However, in the case of XR technologies for off-highway machinery, there is the necessity to at least fine-tune the existing algorithms on the data from real operations. As it can require recording of an excessive amount of data from the operation side, this can lead to storing the additional data after operation. These data can include bystander data, which were collected

without their explicit consent. Moreover, it would not be possible to take the data out of the system if the bystanders request it.

4.3 Privacy guidelines

We present the Guidelines in the following way: First, we discuss the concerns addressed by the recommendation. Next, we show the measures that should be taken by the design team. We then explain how to measure, from the user's perspective, whether we have achieved the goal. Finally, we propose several ideas for user-centred design for development and evaluation recommendations for the Guidelines.

4.3.1 Transparency on different levels of designing the XR-enhancements

Transparency is one of the core principles of the European Data Protection framework [31]; however, within the framework of GDPR, it is usually understood only as an obligation to provide communication with the data subject in a clear and consistent way. In the proposed Guidelines, we apply a broader definition of transparency, extending it to all communication between different developing entities and stakeholders within the framework of joint co-design and collaboration. The development of XR enhancements for off-highway machinery usually requires a combined effort from different groups of developers in collaboration with industrial stakeholders to ensure the development is properly integrated into the existing processes of exploitation and maintenance of the vehicle. To ensure the joint development does not create unexpected privacy-related leaks, we propose the implementation of comprehensive, collaborative, repeated privacy risk assessments and continuous monitoring of data handling practices from all involved stakeholders. This approach will help identify potential vulnerabilities and ensure compliance with data protection regulations throughout the development lifecycle. Additionally, establishing clear communication channels and protocols among all parties involved will foster a culture of transparency and trust, ultimately contributing to the successful integration of XR enhancements in off-highway machinery. We also stress the importance of transparent and clear communication of privacy-related processes with the end user and integrating the end users into the co-design team for the solutions developed from the early stages of development.

On the developing side, we propose the following recommendations:

- **Each member of the interdisciplinary team should identify and present the specific data they need to collect to other team members; the new data request should be evaluated.**
- **Make a specification which disclose what data is collected, used for, and with whom it is shared;**
- **Establish a clear chain of communication for reporting privacy concerns or incidents, ensuring that all team members know whom to contact and what steps to follow;**
- **Implement a feedback loop where team members can provide input on privacy practices and suggest improvements, ensuring continuous enhancement of privacy measures;**
- **Assure and test that end-users be able to find accessible (understandable) information on privacy settings and data usage within the XR interface;**
- **Assure that if collected data are used for taking any human resources decisions (e.g., promotions), the user can clearly understand how the data is translated in evaluation.**

To implement these recommendations, we propose the following methods (this list and the following lists of implementation ideas are not exhaustive):

- Interdisciplinary seminars involving members of the development team, dedicated to discussing implemented technologies from the perspectives of data flow and data collection (the tentative protocol, applied in THEIA^{XR} project is available in Appendix);
- Testing prototypes (from early versions to developed ones) with users to assess the solutions' understandability and applicability via ethical co-design workshops. (the tentative protocol used in the THEIA^{XR} project is available in D.3.3);
- Appointing team members responsible for evaluating data practices from privacy and ethics perspectives.

4.3.2 User-centred control over the system and overreliance protection

As discussed in the relevant literature, user agency and control over their actions (including privacy-related decisions) in XR are keystones to ensuring ethical soundness and an appropriate level of privacy protection within the systems [1]. In the case of XR enhancements in Off-Highway machinery, the end user is usually already an expert in work-related machine operation and has a proper mental model of the process. Introducing unswitchable innovative elements can not only be useless for the experienced expert but also disruptive to the workflow, creating a sense of anger and reactance to the proposed changes. Following Norman's principle of UX design, we advocate for a high level of possible customization for the proposed XR features. We also stress that if the development team identifies certain features that cannot be switched off for various reasons, they should discuss these features in detail with the end users to ensure they will not cause disruption across different modalities of use. Specifically for privacy-related features, we suggest applying the tailored privacy-settings control proposed by [1] to ensure the user can understand the consequences of switching certain features on and off and make an informed decision about the preferred level of data sharing.

We propose the following recommendations:

- **Implement granular controls for feature activation and data collection and sharing (from the user side);**
- **In the early stages of the project, decide which features (elements) will have the option to opt in or opt out;**
- **Provide an explanation for the functionalities from which one cannot opt-out;**
- **Ensure that the end user can easily turn features on or off, including those that collect personal data;**
- **Ensure that the end user is properly informed about the positive and negative effects of activating or deactivating features;**
- **Incorporate visual and audio cues to alert users when data collection is active, ensuring they are always aware of their data privacy status.**

The following methods can help achieve these goals:

- Designing interactive scenarios with users, which help explain the trade-off between feature benefits and risks (the co-design scenario development is discussed in D3.2);
- Conduct an in-depth interview with end-users to determine their desired trade-off between privacy and use of their data (interview protocol is available in D2.3)

4.3.3 Data collection and data storage specification

The expert and internal research project stakeholders insisted that in the current state-of-the-art industries, the machines hardly collect any significant amount of personal data, and that data is usually stored inside the machines. However, with the further development of technologies such as teleoperation, vehicle fleet management, and performance optimization, the need to collect and store more data will rise. This includes data about the operator's actions (which, in certain conditions, can be considered personal data) and the surroundings (including the possibility of collecting data on bystanders). This means that an important part of developing XR-enhancement for the future of off-highway machinery will be to allow for more extensive data collection and, within the framework of privacy-by-design, ensure that this collection is conducted in a privately and ethically sound manner.

We propose the following steps to achieving that:

- **Determine high-level purposes for the data collection (e.g., increase efficiency, develop a more fulfilling working experience) and verify them with relevant stakeholders and end-users.**
- **Determine where the collected data will be stored (locally or in the cloud), how long it will be stored, and for which purposes it will be used (now and in the future).**
- **Minimize data collection to only what is necessary for XR functionality and safety (prioritize data minimization).**
- **If the data collected for a system's training includes personal data, the end-user should be informed about it.**

To achieve these goals, we propose the following measures:

- Interdisciplinary seminars involving members of the development team are dedicated to the implemented technologies from the perspectives of data flow and data collection. (In Theia XR project performed in D2.2, specific data about the flow was used to develop the questionnaire about privacy risks in D2.3 and in an extended discussion with the members of the stakeholders' team in privacy workshops, described in D2.3)
- Developing an interactive map for each type of data collected and stored within the data flow, including personal data processed.
- Conduct a privacy-centered workshop within existing privacy risk assessment methodologies to determine the possible privacy threats of the selected types of data collection (in the THEIA^{XR} project, we applied the LINDDUN methodology; the process was described in D2.3.)

4.3.4 Design for auditability

As pointed out by Norval et al [28], auditability is crucial in ensuring the transparency and accountability of XR systems and, therefore, affects the ethical and privacy dimensions of the development. Effective auditability supports stakeholders' understanding, which is important given the integration of XR technologies with their physical (operational) environments and existing workflows. Auditability is extremely important in multistakeholder development and integration, as in the case of the off-highway machinery XR implementations. It involves creating mechanisms that enable the reconstruction or unpacking of a system's data outputs and input showing how they were used in operational context. In the off-highway machinery domain, we predominantly focus on auditability in the context of incident investigation and analysis. The

stakeholders agree that it is necessary to have a procedure that can handle extreme cases of operation and/or incidents where it is possible to collect a larger amount of data/personal data that is not collected during standard operations. At the same time, this type of data collection and handling should be covered by the developed privacy handling procedures and clearly communicated to the end user.

In relation to audibility, we propose the following:

- **Implement mechanisms for stakeholders and auditors to verify data collection practices and usage;**
- **Specify scenarios and use-cases in which audit can occur;**
- **Designate specific data points that are critical for auditing purposes;**
- **Develop a protocol for internal audit of the data collection practices;**
- **Appoint internal auditors in the project from the project members;**
- **Engage a range of stakeholders in the repeated audit process to ensure that the audit data serves the interests of all parties involved and enhances system accountability;**
- **End users should have clear and accessible information about what data is being audited and how it is used (e.g., in case of incidents holding);**
- **End users should have mechanisms to review or request deletion of their audit data after the audit, if applicable (e.g., if the system collects personal data);**

To ensure the implementation of audibility, it is necessary to:

- Involve the stakeholders in revising their privacy goals constantly and specify the cases where the different modes of data collection can occur by prompting the discussion via privacy-related workshops.
- Prompting interdisciplinary and inter companies collaboration for creating the audit standards for off-highway machinery XR.

4.3.5 Design for achieving the appropriate level of trust

The discussions with the end users and designers revealed that one of the potential problems with the implementation of XR features into the working processes of off-highway machinery is the difficulty in achieving the proper level of trust from the operators. On one hand, experienced operators may find the new features distracting, diverting their attention from the real-world environment. On the other hand, junior operators exposed to these features from the very beginning might develop a habit of relying on them excessively, which can create different types of risks (e.g., mixing real and virtual objects and lowering awareness of real-world objects) [2]. To mitigate this problem, it is necessary to ensure that the implemented XR-enhancement system allows the operator to customize its features and provides clear cues to prevent overreliance.

We suggest the following steps to mitigate the risks:

- **Analyze the proposed features for their potential to distort the perception of reality or provoke overreliance. Conduct an assessment of each feature to identify any aspects that might lead operators to misinterpret or overly depend on virtual information;**
- **Develop the XR interface, which can be adjusted to the operator's experience level, and incorporate customizable features to allow operators to adjust the XR system to their preferences;**

- **For features that cannot be turned off or adjusted, the operator should receive a clear explanation of why the feature cannot be disabled;**
- **Implement training programs that focus on explaining the boundaries of the technologies, their potential pitfalls and the optimal way of using virtual information;**
- **Assure that the end users will be able to efficiently control the process of operation and take the decision independently.**

As a method of implementing the ideas, we propose the following methods:

- Co-designing workshops for designing visual and auditory cues within the XR interface to help users maintain control over the features;
- Comparison of augmented and existing workflows to determine potential points that may provoke overreliance (e.g., moments of prolonged high load);
- Workshops with operators about the implementation of the features (D3.3 includes the workshop guide used in the THEIA^{XR} project).

4.3.6 Privacy protection for bystanders

As shown in previous works, capturing bystanders' information can pose a significant risk to their privacy rights due to the potential for connecting the data with external datasets [26, 30]. To mitigate these risks, XR implementations should be designed to minimize the storage of bystanders' data and opt for technologies that collect less personally identifiable information. Additionally, adopting privacy-preserving techniques, such as anonymization, can help protect bystanders' identities even if their data is incidentally collected. It is also crucial to inform bystanders about possible data collection in the area, similar to the approach in [26].

We propose the following recommendations for developing the system for bystanders' privacy protection:

- **Prioritize methods of information collection that are less privacy-invasive (e.g., using thermal cameras instead of video capture for obstacle recognition);**
- **Design multiple mechanisms to protect the identity of bystanders, including anonymization techniques and appropriate cryptographic schemes;**
- **Develop methods to notify bystanders about data collection; it would be useful to double the warnings to ensure they are not missed (e.g., in the case of off-highway machinery, it can be helpful to place warnings about the collection of surrounding information both on the vehicle and near the entrances of the operation area);**
- **If by any reasons data anonymisation is not possible, establish a process for bystanders to request the deletion of their data.**

To helping applying the recommendation we propose the following methods:

- Co-designing the warning signals system with the stakeholders and end-users to be sure they are recognisable and fit the context of data collection;
- Discuss the privacy-friendly alternative solutions for data collection via privacy-oriented focus groups.

4.3.7 AI in XR solutions for off-highway machinery

There are multiple ways AI can be used in the domain of XR solutions for off-highway machinery. For example, it can be used in developing and updating algorithms for collision avoidance [27], optimizing user control and feedback during teleoperation, and providing real-time suggestions for performance optimization by guiding the use of visual and XR cues [25]. There has been significant progress in the domain of industrial robot teleoperation and the operation of autonomous vehicles; however, it is necessary to tailor these solutions to the domain of off-highway machinery using data from machine and operator performance. In a broader sense, the development of any AI solutions for XR-related implementations in the off-highway vehicles domain should also follow the general guidelines for ethical AI development, including addressing the questions of transparency, reliability, justice, etc. [8, 21].

To ensure high ethical and privacy standards in AI development, we propose the following recommendations:

- **Any algorithm implemented in XR solutions should be tested for fairness (e.g., in the case of obstacle detection, it should equally recognize people with different skin colours).**
- **Prioritize the use of transparent and explainable algorithms whenever possible.**
- **Ensure that the data used to fine-tune the algorithms for the domain of off-highway machinery does not collect privacy-sensitive data.**
- **If the algorithms are fine-tuned on data from real operations, inform the operator of the use of the data for that purpose.**

To helping applying the recommendation we propose the following methods:

- Include the specialist in AI privacy and ethics into the developing group to assure the possible issues are addressing on the early stage of the project;
- Internally audit the datasets and algorithms used in the developing project to assure they are in line with project privacy goals (similar to [20]).

5 Conclusions

While XR technologies are becoming increasingly prevalent in various industries, their use in the off-highway machinery domain is still relatively rare. This presents a challenge in developing them within the frameworks of privacy-preserving and ethical work practices. Although there are well-developed initiatives covering various ethical and privacy aspects in XR, we believe that more specific guidelines addressing the unique aspects of XR applications in the off-highway machinery domain can be beneficial for developers and stakeholders. This first version of the privacy guidelines aims to bridge this gap through a detailed analysis of existing initiatives in XR and the experience of XR development for off-highway machinery, as performed in THEIA^{XR}. The current version will be further discussed and developed throughout the project lifecycle in close collaboration with project stakeholders and the broader XR community. The results will be presented in deliverable D7.6 “Design guidelines and validation reports for privacy (final version).

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Appendix

Semi-structured interview about the existing privacy-related workflow, list of the high-level questions.

(Experts were asked to provide a baseline for current industrial standards in the field of their machinery operations not focusing on specific company/country).

1. Does the vehicle typically collect (or can potentially collect, e.g. the feature exists in the new machines but was not present in the older models) some types of information such as:

- GPS data,
- data about the speed of movement,
- directions of the movement,
- environmental conditions (like temperature),
- (any) terrain analysis data (such as ground composition and slope),
- (any) obstacle information through sensors or cameras,
- operational efficiency metrics (e.g. fuel usage),
- safety-related data (proximity alerts and collision warnings).

If any of that is collected, where and how this information is typically stored? How long is it usually stored? If there any additional industry-shared rules for longer storage in case of incidents?

2. How does authorization for vehicles use occur, step-by-step? Where is the authorization data stored?

3. How is access to the data typically managed? Has the companies considered scenarios where operators request access to their data (if you ever heard about these types of requests)? If so, what types of data might they inquire about?

4. Does the vehicles monitor any vital signals from the operator (e.g. fatigue levels/ alertness through eye tracking). If yes, where does it store?

5. If the operator leaves the company, what usually happens to the data associated with them (e.g., performance data, if they are collected)?

6. Have the companies usually implement any analytical approaches to the data? Do the data used for promotion/salary decision? Do the data use for other purposes, e.g. AI models training?

7. If there are any standard consent forms in the industry, explaining the operators GDPR related issues connected to their work or each company implement their own forms?

8. Are there any fleet management systems used to coordinate vehicles? If yes, how do they work, what types of data are collected, and how is the data stored (e.g., is the cloud hosting internal to the company or external)? Can end-users (operators) choose whether to use fleet-management-related features, or is their use typically mandatory in the contract?

9. What is industrial opinion about teleoperation and automatic operations? What are the barriers to implement the teleoperations and automatic operations in the area.

ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

AI	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
AR	AUGMENTED REALITY
CCPA	CALIFORNIA CONSUMER PRIVACY ACT
E3XR	ANALITICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ETHICAL, EDUCATIONAL AND EUDAMONIC XR DESIGN
GDPR	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION
VR	VIRTUAL REALITY
XR	EXTENDED REALITY
XRSI	X REALITY SAFETY INTELLIGENCE